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Holistic decision-making for climate & environment

Deliverable 2.5: Programmatic, process, and political performance of environmental policies in the European Union.

Taking a stab in the dark of your anticipations: The effects of the building codes in the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2010 with a spotlight on Germany and the Netherlands

LEGAL DISCLAIMER

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Scope of the document	In this task, we conduct an in-depth, ex-post evaluation of the performance of select

environmental policies at the regional, national, and EU level. We define performance broadly to encompass the programmatic (goal attainment, co-benefits for instance for public health, effectiveness, equity for instance based on gender and socioeconomic status), process (innovativeness, legitimacy, policy resilience), and political (governance capacity, public values, reputation) dimension of the policy (McConnell, 2010; McConnell et al., 2020). We review the literature on environmental policy, program evaluation, and policy success to identify the characteristics that influence these dimensions of policy performance. We select key environmental policies at different levels of government for an in-depth comparative study through stakeholder consultation. The performance of selected policies is evaluated based on the criteria set out above and the characteristics identified in the literature (Edmondson et al., 2019; Goyal, 2021; Strassheim, 2021). Finally, ex-post performance is compared against ex-ante evaluations, where available, to reflect on how to better anticipate policy consequences and propose improvements to methods and tools for impact assessment. The data is collected through a combination of interviews, news articles, policy documents, and secondary literature and the analysis is conducted using a mixed methods approach. Early findings contribute to the development of economic methods and tools in WP4, the selection of decision-making criteria in Task 5.2, and an understanding of policy resilience in Task 5.4.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The buildings sector is a major source for greenhouse gas emissions and, therefore, requires crafting of successful policies to catalyse climate change mitigation. In this process, ex-ante policy analyses play an invaluable role in assessing effects of a policy, but they often still fail to incorporate important factors into the analysis to predict policy outcomes. In this deliverable, we present the results of an ex-post evaluation of the success of building policies and derive at implications for achieving better and more holistic future ex-ante assessments.

We adopted a qualitative, comparative case study research design and examine the success of the implementation of building codes and standards from the European Union's (EU) recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2010/31/EU), focusing on the Netherlands and Germany. Data sources included 11 scientific publications, 36 policy documents, reports and press releases, 39 news articles, and 17 semi-structured interviews conducted by the authors.

Based on this material, we assessed the programmatic, process and political success over time for these policies and contrast both cases to understand better the factors that lead to different success outcomes, considering changes over time and disruptions. We compared our evaluation with ex-ante assessments, where available, and derived lessons for how to better anticipate policy consequences and lessons that can be used to improve future policies in the construction sector.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Long text
BENG	Nearly zero energy buildings (Dutch: Bijna Energieneutrale Gebouwen)
BPIE	Buildings Performance Institute Europe
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
EnEV	Energy Saving Ordinance (German: Energieeinsparungsverordnung)
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
GEG	Building Energy Act (German: Gebäudeenergiegesetz)
GHG	Greenhouse gas
JRC	Joint Research Center of the European Commission
KfW	Credit Institute for Reconstruction (German: Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau)
kWh/m²	Kilowatt-hours per square meter
MS	Member States of the European Union
Mt	Megatonnes
NZEB	Nearly zero energy buildings
NTA	Dutch technical agreement (Dutch: Nederlands technische afspraak)
RVO	The Netherlands Enterprise Agency (Dutch: Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland)
TWh	Terrawatt-hours
UNFCCC	The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

Section 1

Introduction

Buildings contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions. Approximately 40% of EU energy consumption and 36% of its CO₂ emissions are related to buildings. The EU has directives that affect policies for climate change mitigation in many countries (i.e. EU Member States (MS')) and, therefore, may catalyse higher policy ambition. For buildings, the EU has most notably adopted the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), which MS' then are required to implement at the national level (Economidou et al., 2020). In the 2010 recast of the EPBD (Directive (EU) 2010/31), for example, new minimum energy performance requirements for new buildings were introduced to make them nearly zero energy buildings (NZEB). Further minimum energy performance requirements were expanded to all existing buildings that undergo major renovations.

These policies often aim to mitigate emissions from the construction, operation, and demolition of buildings, for example by introducing policies that address building codes, heating sources and renovations of buildings. To reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the buildings sector, we need effective policies. Impact assessments and macro-economic modelling are used to foresee the effectiveness of the intended policies. Effectiveness relates to “whether policy goals have been achieved and whether this can be attributed to the policy” (Huitema et al., 2011). However, such assessments are often not holistic, and there is often a lack of evidence on the actual performance of existing policies. However, it is important to holistically evaluate the effects of climate policies, for example, through qualitative methods, because they can complement quantitative policy analyses by incorporating additional criteria that may not be easy to quantify. Further, such qualitative empirical evaluations can help to understand how actual policy performance might have differed from expectations. These lessons can facilitate policy learning to improve future policy designs, as well as improve the accuracy of ex-ante evaluation frameworks.

Current reviews of the effectiveness of policy instruments for climate mitigation in buildings find that building regulations are one of the most effective policy instruments and at the same time offer co-benefits in combating energy poverty (Cocker, 2025; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007). However, despite their presence in EU policies, emissions in the building sector have not decreased significantly over the past years (EEA, n.d.), so an evaluation of the EU building codes could nuance this view. Further, energy policy papers often do not holistically evaluate policies, and in

the present evaluations of climate policy, there is often a gap between evaluation theory and practice (Huitema et al., 2011; Trosvik et al., 2023).

The measurement of the performance of policies has been the focus of academic literature on policy evaluation. Various approaches have been developed with different emphases, for example to understand “policy fiascoes” (Bovens & Hart, 1996), or policy successes (Bovens et al., 2001; Hart & Compton, 2019). The focus on success proved to be a more fruitful framing in terms of learning from what makes policies successful. A policy is considered successful if “it achieves the goals that proponents set out to achieve and attracts no criticism of any significance and/or support is virtually universal” (McConnell, 2010a, p. 351). Therefore, success of a policy has been identified across three dimensions (McConnell, 2010a): (1) Programmatic success entails attaining the intended policy goals; (2) Process success is about whether the policy-making process was successful; and (3) Political success occurs if the effect of the policy has benefits for political reputation. However, there are no applications of this framework in the building sector, and the programmatic dimension lacks specification of what program success entails in the building sector.

In this deliverable, we apply a policy evaluation framework with these three success dimensions to an EU building directive. Our aim is to evaluate the implementation of EU building policies for better anticipating the performance of EU energy policies. We chose the EPBD as a policy, because it is the main EU policy that includes building codes for climate mitigation. We focus on the 2010 recast, because it contained important reforms for new buildings and renovations, and it was transposed a while ago, so its effects can be fully evaluated. While we consider EU related insights on all MS, we particularly zoom in on the transposition in two MS to get a more detailed idea of the effects of the EPBD at different scales. We focus on Germany and the Netherlands as frontrunners in the buildings sector, to distil lessons for successful implementation of the EPBD and its building codes, the minimum energy performance requirements. Another aim is to test whether McConnell's (2010a) policy success framework is applicable in the context of policies for climate mitigation in buildings in the EU and its MS, especially regarding the programmatic dimension. We ask:

To what extent can the building codes and standards from the EPBD 2010 be considered as a policy success?

- How successful is the EPBD 2010 in terms of programmatic, process, and political success?
- What can be learnt from this for ex-ante policy evaluations?

This report continues with some background information on the EPBD 2010, and its transposition in the Netherlands and Germany (Section 2). It then presents our evaluation framework (Section 3) and the assessment methodology (Section 4). Our findings are described in Section 5, structured by country, and in the same sequence

of program success, process success, and political success. Lastly, we conclude by summarizing our findings, comparing the three cases, and discussing implications for EU decision-making, as well as ex-ante decision-making frameworks (Section 6).

Section 2

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EU) 2010/31

The EPBD recast from 2010 was adopted on May 19, 2010 and included the following provisions. It requires new buildings to fulfil NZEB standards from January 2019 for buildings occupied by public authorities and from January 2021 for all new buildings (Article 9). The definition of NZEBs is left to the MS' and only requires the use of a numerical indicator of primary energy use expressed in kWh/m² per year. MS also need to specify intermediate targets for improving the energy performance of new buildings by 2015, and provide information on national requirements and measures concerning the use of energy from renewable sources in new buildings and existing buildings undergoing major renovation.

The EPBD recast also eliminates the previous 1000m² threshold for minimum energy performance standards for existing buildings that undergo major renovation (Article 7). In addition, it introduces energy performance requirements for technical building systems (e.g., heating, hot water, ventilation, cooling, air conditioning) (Article 8). It also requires the calculation of cost-optimal levels of minimum energy performance every 5 years, and the alignment of minimum energy performance requirements with cost-optimal levels (Article 5). Cost-optimal levels describe those energy performance levels of energy efficiency technology (e.g. heating boilers, insulation), where additional upfront costs are later amortized through avoided costs for energy consumption (Economidou et al., 2020). There are a few other novel requirements, for example, on Energy Performance Certificates that are out of scope of this study, given the focus on minimum energy performance requirements. The EPBD has been formally evaluated by the European Commission in 2016 (European Commission, 2016b) in the context of the development of a proposal for an amendment of the EPBD, which was finally adopted in 2018 as Directive (EU) 2018/844.

In both countries, we will only focus on those parts of these policies that relate to the EPBD implementation of minimum energy performance standards, and not additional national or regional policies. The following policies apply to this: in Germany, minimum energy performance requirements already existed previously in the Energy Saving Ordinance (*Energieeinsparungsverordnung* – EnEV, 2001) and are

based on the annual primary energy demand of a reference building. The energy performance of buildings is also often described by the reference values of the KfW ('Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau' – 'Credit Institute for Reconstruction'), which is a state-owned investment and development bank that operates the funding schemes for energy efficient buildings (see table for a comparison of the values). In the EnEV reform of 2013 (EnEV, 2013) the requirements for new buildings were lowered by 25% from a KfW100 standard to the KfW 70 standard, with enforcement starting from 2016. Requirements for buildings undergoing major renovations, as well as building components and technical building systems already existed and met the EPBD requirements. The EnEV was included in the Building Energy Act in 2020 (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG) (Horward & Rosenberger, 2020). In 2022, a reform of the GEG introduced a further tightening of the standards of new buildings by 20% to KfW55. Enforcement of the building standards is exercised via building permits, but only for new buildings and major renovations. Minor renovations do not require a building permit.

In the Netherlands, plans for new energy performance requirements for new buildings following the EPBD from 2010 were included in the *Bouwbesluit* (Building Decree) in 2012 (Bouwbesluit, 2012). Standards existed since 1996 and are based on an energy performance coefficient (*Energieprestatiecoëfficiënt*) and specified in the Energy Performance Standards for Buildings (NEN 7120) (NEN, 2012). This coefficient was reduced from 0.8 to 0.6 (for residential buildings) in 2012 following "national plan to promote NZEBs". Later in 2015, this coefficient was even further reduced to 0.4, while at the same time proposing provisional requirements for NZEBs ('Bijna Energie Neutrale Gebouwen' – BENG). A cost-effectiveness study in 2018 then led to an adjustment of the BENG requirements, which were finally adopted in December 2019, and specified in the new standard NTA8800 that came into force in 2021. There are three requirements on which BENG is based: i) BENG 1 – the total energy demand of the building in kWh/m² per year; ii) BENG 2 – the primary fossil fuel demand in kWh/m² per year; and iii) BENG 3 – the share of renewable energy in the total energy (mix) of a given building. Existing buildings that undergo major renovations have also been addressed in the Building Decree 2012 through minimum requirements for building components that came into force 2013–2014 (van Cruchten, 2020). There are also standards for building components, such as roofs, floors and facades. Further, since 2020 there are requirements for technical building systems (van Cruchten, 2020; van Eck, 2015). The minimum energy requirements for new buildings, and buildings that undergo major renovation are also enforced by issuing building permits.

Section 3

Conceptual framework

Evaluations of building policy (Cocker, 2025; Ürge-Vorsatz et al., 2007) often roughly follow the evaluation guidelines of the IPCC report (Dubash et al., 2023). These include the following criteria: environmental effectiveness; economic effectiveness; distributional effects; co-benefits and negative side effects; institutional requirements; and transformative potential. A more elaborate evaluation framework for the building sector has recently been developed by Edmondson et al. (2024), who build on these criteria and detail indicators, as well as add criteria of fiscal burden, acceptance, and governance.

In the more theoretical literature on evaluation in the academic discipline of policy sciences, evaluation approaches can be grouped into rationalist and constructivist approaches. For rationalist approaches, the success of a policy can be objectively measured against different criteria. Constructivist approaches acknowledge that success is a subjective interpretation that require a reflexive and participatory model of assessment (Guba & Lincoln, 1989).

McConnell (2010a) has set out an approach that combines both perspectives pragmatically, and focusses on the identification of policy successes, rather than policy failures. He points out that policy success rarely fits within a binary of success or failure, but instead there are different degrees of success, ranging from failure, to precarious, conflicted, or resilient success, to policy success. These gradients of success occur in the different dimensions of the program, process and politics of a policy (McConnell, 2010b):

1. Programmatic success entails attaining the intended policy goals
2. Process success is about the way in which policymaking and implementation took place
3. Political success results from the interactions of actors and interests in policy-making arenas

Other policy evaluation frameworks, such as from Hart and Compton (2019) list temporality as another category of policy success, based on the work of Bovens and Hart (1996). However, we follow other evaluation scholars, which have reflected that such a specification is inaccurate, and acknowledged that success is temporal in each of the three dimensions (Goyal, 2021; Newman & Head, 2015).

For our analysis, we have followed McConnell's (2010a) framework, and complemented it with indicators from climate and building policy evaluations, because McConnell's framework is not domain specific (see *Table 1*). The program dimension contains firstly whether the implementation of the policy is in line with its objectives. That means if the policy output, or the final policy design meets the objectives of the policy that were defined at the outset of creating the policy. Second, program success also entails the achievement of outcomes in reality. In the case of climate mitigation in the building sector, these are GHG emissions, and energy consumption. Another indicator involves whether the policy creates a benefit for the target group, or distributional effects, as well as fairness. These target groups could for example be insulation or construction industries, building owners and tenants, but they could also be future generations, the world, and all its inhabitants – even non-human. The final indicator in the program dimension summarizes domain criteria. This includes whether climate mitigation technologies (e.g. heat pumps, insulation) amortize the additional upfront costs in comparison to conventional fossil technologies through energy savings over their lifetime (cost-effectiveness). It further includes the fiscal burden of the policy on the government budget, and other potential co-benefits and trade-offs, such as the spread of renewable technologies, living comfort, and so forth.

Table 1: Our evaluation framework for building policies

PROGRAMMATIC SUCCESS	PROCESS SUCCESS	POLITICAL SUCCESS
Meeting objectives	Preserving policy goals and instruments	Enhancing electoral prospects or reputation of governments and leaders
Producing desired outcomes Energy Use, GHG emissions	Conferring legitimacy	Controlling the policy agenda and easing the business of governing
Creating a benefit for the target group	Building a sustainable coalition	Sustaining the broad values and direction of government
Meeting policy domain criteria	Opposition to process	Opposition to political benefits for government
Opposition to program aims		

Source: based on McConnell (2010a), with complementary indicators from Huitema et al. (2011), Dubash et al. (2023), and Edmondson et al. (2024)

The first indicator in the process dimension is about whether the initial policy goals and instruments have been preserved throughout the policy process, or whether they needed to be amended. Next, a process is successful, if it confers legitimacy to a policy, for example if it followed legal and normal procedures, and involved stakeholder consultation. A third indicator concerns the creation of a sustainable coalition that supports the policy, beyond initial adoption.

Political success consists of the reputation and electoral prospects for government or leaders that can be gained through a policy. This may entail acceptance among population, firms and political actors. Another criterion is the control a policy can exert over the policy agenda, even if it is only showcasing to deal with the problem at hand. A third criterion is the extent to which the policy helps to maintain the broad values and the direction of the government. A policy for climate mitigation in buildings can for example contribute to the broader agenda of reducing GHG emissions. As a last criterion, opposition is added in each dimension to capture opposition to program aims, the process, or the political benefits for government.

Section 4

Methodology

We adopt an embedded, comparative case study design (Yin, 2018) to explore the policy success of the EPBD at EU level, and zooming in on two similar EU MS, the Netherlands and Germany. A qualitative research approach was adopted, gathering evidence from academic literature, policy documents, reports, interviews and news articles. We also added evidence from three bachelor thesis projects—supervised by the first author—on the success of the Dutch NZEB transposition from the perspective of government, construction sector, and housing associations. We conducted an analysis of policy success based on our synthesis of McConnell's (2010a) framework in Section 2. We then compared the three cases to understand better the factors that lead to different success outcomes. This will add to the lack of empirical insights about the success of policies for climate mitigation in the building sector.

Subsection 4.1: Data collection

Our study covers the time span from 2008, when the Commission drafted the EPBD proposal until May 2025, and all empirical material relates to this time span. First, we searched for articles that analyse NZEB policies in the three cases on the databases of Scopus. We conducted various searches by combining selected keywords that include various terms to describe the case, the building sector, policy, evaluation and the climate aspect (*Table 2*). The individual searches and search results were not documented. We included articles in the search results when they covered insights on the policy design, policy process and the impact of the relevant policies (see Section 2). This resulted in the inclusion of 11 scientific publications.

Table 2: List of keywords grouped by terminology for searching for academic articles on Scopus

CASES	BUILDINGS	POLICY	EVALUATIONS	CLIMATE
Dutch	Building	Policy	Evaluation	Decarbonization
Netherlands	Heating	Building code	Success	Mitigation
Germany	Housing		Effect(iveness)	Climate
German	Energy efficiency		Assessment	Emissions
EPBD			(ex post) impact	

Energieeinsparungs- gesetz			Appraisal	
Nearly zero emission buildings (NZEB)				

To find relevant policy documents, we performed Google searches with similar combinations of keywords and consulted websites of the Dutch and German national governments. We selected the policy documents that covered the respective policies, as well as reports and studies that evaluate the concerned policies. This resulted in the inclusion of 36 policy documents, reports, and press releases.

To find relevant news articles in Dutch and German media that would provide additional information about the policy process and evaluations or links to relevant actors, we browsed Nexis Uni. We selected one major centre-left daily newspaper, and one magazine for professionals in the buildings sector in each country in order to cover both broader public debates, as well as sector-specific debates. For the Netherlands, this was “de Volkskrant” and “Cobouw”, and for Germany, this was “Süddeutsche Zeitung” and “Immobilien Zeitung”. We then applied the following search queries: “bijna energie neutrale gebouwen”; “renovatie AND gebouw AND energie”; “Niedrigstenergiegebäude”; “Energieeinsparverordnung AND Sanierung”; “Gebäudeenergiegesetz AND Sanierung”. We only included articles from 2010 until May 2025. After cleaning up the data from articles that did not contain insights about the specified policies, in total 39 articles were retrieved (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Further, we added relevant articles, policy documents and reports from the bachelor theses. All identified material is listed in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 3: Number of retrieved articles after source

SÜDDEUTSCHE ZEITUNG	15
IMMOBILIEN ZEITUNG	15
DE VOLKSKRANT	0
COBOUW	9

Lastly, we conducted semi-structured interviews with different actors in the building sector. We contacted representatives from ministries and governmental agencies, research institutes, interest groups, and consultancies in each of the cases. We used Microsoft Teams to record, and automatically transcribe the conversations that evolved around an interview guide (**Error! Reference source not found.**), which was adapted to the background of each interviewee and to which follow-up questions were added as made sense in the natural flow of the interview. The interviews took

between 43 minutes and 103 minutes. We interviewed a total of 17 people at EU level and national levels in Germany and the Netherlands. The set consisted of technical staff from ministries and governmental agencies, researchers from private and governmental research institutes, and policy advisers from industry associations (see *Table 4*).

Table 4: Distribution of interviewees across cases and professions

	EU	NL	GER
TECHNICAL STAFF	2	3	
RESEARCHERS		2	3
POLICY ADVISORS		7	

The distribution of interviewees is asymmetrical with an overrepresentation of Dutch interviewees because we included 9 interviews from the bachelor theses that were exclusively about the Dutch case. Further, there were availability issues of the German ministry, as the empirical research was conducted following the German federal elections from February 2025, after which major reorganization of the relevant ministries took place. However, this interviewee asymmetry is balanced by newspaper articles, which adequately represent the German case. Of course, this is not an exhaustive set of interviewees and news articles to evaluate all the complexities of the three cases. Nevertheless, all sources taken together represent a comprehensive dataset that robustly provides insights into the main categories relevant for an overview evaluation of the three cases and the three dimensions.

Subsection 4.2 Data analysis

The interviews were recorded and automatically transcribed in MS Teams. The transcripts were corrected and then coded all material based on the coding scheme (**Error! Reference source not found.**). We followed the criteria of success for each dimension that we identified in our theoretical framework. For the coding we utilize Atlas.ti 9.0.18 for Windows (Scientific Software Development GmbH, 2023). Our study uses a qualitative content analysis by summarizing the main messages from the quotations in each indicator of the policy success heuristic and creating a narrative of those evaluations. Then, we assessed the degree of success based on the assessment tables from McConnell (2010a) (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Next, we compared the two cases and reflected on success factors based on the differences in policy process and design in each case. Furthermore, we derived lessons for the design of the EPBD at EU level, and lastly, we compared our evaluation results with ex-ante assessments, where available, to determine whether predictions were accurate.

Section 5

Success of the EPBD at EU level

Subsection 5.1: Program Success

Subsection 5.1.1: Meeting objectives

With regards to whether the objectives of the EPBD were met in implementation, a report by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in the European Commission in 2021 finds that all MS' implemented the EPBD requirements on minimum energy performance requirements (Zangheri et al., 2021). Earlier, all MS were found to have gaps and errors in the transposition of the EPBD, particularly regarding minimum energy requirements. These were then addressed successfully in infringement procedures (European Commission, 2016b), and then the EPBD was identified as "the main driving force behind significant improvements in the energy used in EU buildings" (European Commission, 2016c). It was also considered coherent, both internally, and with other EU objectives and interventions (European Commission, 2016b; European Commission, 2016c). However, according to the public consultation for the EPBD amendment in 2018, the EPBD so far failed to harmonize national building regulations, which was one of the aims of introducing the EPBD. It also failed to ensure the same level of ambition at the national level, and it failed to establish comparable standards between countries (Boermans et al., 2015). Further, the implementation of the directive could be more efficient with regards to transparency, the fragmentation of markets, and complexity (European Commission, 2016c).

For example, MS use different indicators to define a NZEB, and even where they are similar, calculation methodologies vary. The standards vary from 15 to 95 kWh/m² per year, partly also because of climatically different demands for energy use (D'Agostino et al., 2025; Zangheri et al., 2021; D'Agostino et al., 2021; D'Agostino & Mazzarella, 2019; Erhorn-Kluttig and Erhorn, 2018a; Erhorn-Kluttig and Erhorn, 2018b; Annunziata et al., 2013). Nevertheless, NZEB definitions have continuously become more ambitious since the introduction of the EPBD in 2010 and were by 2025 about 70% lower than national requirements in 2006 (D'Agostino, 2025; Zangheri et al., 2021; D'Agostino et al., 2021; Interview 3). Further, MS mostly seem to align NZEBs standards with cost-optimal levels, or even make them more ambitious than cost-optimal (D'Agostino et al., 2025). However, almost all MS' failed to meet the benchmark standards recommended by

the Commission in 2016 (European Commission, 2016a). Moreover, there is less information available on whether and how MS' implemented the requirements for major renovations, building components, and technical building systems.

Other important aspects of implementing the objectives are enforcement mechanisms and compliance. The EU stakeholder consultation and evaluation reports mention "poor compliance and enforcement of national measures" (European Commission, 2016c; Boermans et al., 2015). The compliance rates on the ground with implementing the national legislation is estimated to be well above 80% for new buildings, 30% to 79% for major renovations, and 50% to 93% for building components (Jamieson et al., 2015). With this compliance gap, and the lack of comparability between MS', the implementation remains conflicted.

Subsection 5.1.2: Outcomes

There is no ex-post evaluation of the reduction of GHG emissions through the EPBD 2010, and the European Commission asserts that it is, "impossible to precisely segregate and quantify a specific contribution of the EPBD" (European Commission, 2016b). Furthermore, availability and reporting of data by MS' remains a challenge for evaluating the effectiveness of the EPBD (European Commission, 2023). A 2015 public consultation found that stakeholders think that the EPBD, "so far does not effectively address challenges in the energy performance of existing buildings" (Boermans et al., 2015). Nevertheless, the Commission assumes that the EPBD effectively reduces GHG emissions (Interview 3).

In our evaluation, we assume that the effectiveness of the EPBD can be indicated by using GHG emissions in the buildings stock. Monitoring data from the European Environment Agency (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) shows that GHG emissions in the building sector have decreased steadily since around 2010, by 329 Megatonnes (Mt) CO₂ equivalents (or 27.3%) from 1204 Mt in 2011 to 875 Mt in 2020 (EEA, n.d.). However, this is mainly attributed to a decrease in indirect emissions, which derive from the (external) production of electricity and heat that is used in a building. In contrast, direct emissions have been stagnant since 2014 (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Direct emissions are the emissions from fossil fuels used in a building, for example from a gas boiler. They have only been reduced by 57 Mt (11.4%) from 499 Mt in 2011 to 442 Mt in 2020. It should be noted that more optimistic reduction comparisons are possible if the years 2010 and 2022 are included, but these years represent outliers, since 2010 represents a very cold winter in Europe and 2022 is influenced largely by high energy prices due to the energy crisis. The low reductions of direct emissions indicate a lack of installations of renewable heating systems and a lack of insulation efforts (Interview 7). The low impact on emission reductions is plausible, as the provisions on new buildings prevented the addition of new emissions, rather than encouraging emission reduction of the existing building stock (D'Agostino et al., 2021). Moreover, the regulation on major renovations likely also had a low

impact, as there were not many major renovations and the rate of renovation is smaller than the renovation targets of the EU (European Commission, 2016a).

Figure 1: GHG emissions from energy use in buildings in the EU (from European Environment Agency (n.d.))

Figure 2: Direct GHG emissions from energy use in buildings in the EU

The Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE) states that the 14.7% decrease of emissions from 2015 falls short of the goals that were assumed in a central EU buildings emission reduction scenario from the impact assessment of the EPBD 2010. They state that according to the scenario, the EU was expecting a 27.9% decrease of emissions for the same time frame (Amarocho et al., 2024; European Commission, 2008b). They conclude that climate change mitigation in the buildings sector “remains significantly off track”.

Based on slightly differing data, in 2016 the Commission had prepared an evaluation of the EPBD 2010 recast as a preparation for the 2018 amendment. It was based on a decomposition analysis, and found that the EPBD caused CO₂ emission reduction of 63 Mt (i.e., a 10% decrease) between 2007 and 2014, while other factors such as more dwellings and larger homes mitigated this decrease in the overall outcome (European Commission, 2016b).

Another outcome of the EPBD with implications for GHG emissions in the building sector is the energy consumption in buildings (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). It has remained virtually the same since 2010, with recent drops in 2020 and 2022, but it is unclear whether these drops are persistent, or linked to external pressures, such as the energy crisis, cost of living crisis, or rising costs in the construction sector (Interview 7). Nevertheless, a recent assessment from the JRC highlighted an absolute decrease in energy consumption by 30.2 Mt (~7.7%) between 2005 and 2022, with 23.9

Mt in the residential sector and 6.3 Mt in the services sector (Maduta et al., 2025). A previous report by JRC highlighted that energy savings from improvements in energy efficiency would be even higher, but an increasing number of buildings and an increase in energy consumption lowered overall reductions in energy consumption (Zangheri et al., 2021). Lack of energy savings was attributed to low renovation rates, particularly for a very low level of deep renovations (Zangheri et al., 2021).

The 2016 evaluation of the EPBD by the Commission is again based on slightly differing data. Based on a decomposition analysis, it concludes that the EPBD has saved 48.9 Mt of final energy between 2007 and 2014, of which 41.4 Mt have been achieved in the residential sector and 7.5 Mt in the services sector. Energy consumption in 2014 was then at 409.3 Mt final energy consumption, with 263.2Mt in the residential sector and 146.1Mt in the services sector (European Commission, 2016a). It resumes that the effects of the EPBD were in line to achieve the estimated energy savings of 60–80 Mt by 2020 that were assumed in the 2008 impact assessment (European Commission, 2008b). In contrast, the BPIE assessment highlighted that energy consumption only decreased by 2.8% (compared to the pre-set 6.5% target) between 2015 and 2022, and that these reductions were mainly derived from the increase of renewable sources in the electricity mix. However, even the share of renewable energy is considered too low in comparison to the values assumed by the 2008 impact assessment (Amorocho et al., 2024). Overall then, the success of the EPBD regarding the environmental outcomes is precarious with indications for only low reductions of direct emissions and hardly any savings in energy consumption.

Figure 3: Energy consumption in buildings in the EU (from European Environment Agency (n.d.))

Subsection 5.1.3: Domain criteria

There are several other criteria against which the success of the EPBD can be analysed. Firstly, the policy ensures cost-effectiveness, as the requirements are based on cost-optimality studies (D'Agostino et al., 2025; D'Agostino et al., 2021; Zangheri et al., 2021; Zangheri et al., 2022; Interview 3). Secondly, the administrative costs of implementing the EPBD (staff, studies, communication campaign) for the national governments and agencies are estimated at 160.8M€, and are perceived as “reasonable” considering the benefits of the EPBD (European Commission, 2016b). It also does not create regulatory burden as the policy does not mandate any construction or renovation activity. Only in the case of a decision to build or renovate a building does the EPBD prescribe standards to prevent suboptimal investments (European Commission, 2016b).

Thirdly, there are several co-benefits and trade-offs that result from the EPBD. It supports and increases the production of energy from RES (European Commission, 2016b; D'Agostino et al., 2025). It also supports the development of innovative technologies in the building market and leads to a cost reduction of effective technologies (European Commission, 2016b; Erhorn and Erhorn-Kluttig, 2018; Interview 3). For example, a reduction of cost-optimal levels of about 20% has been observed between 2013 and 2020 (Zangheri et al., 2022). It created jobs in the construction sector (European Commission, 2016b; Hughes and Molloy, 2022), and benefits people with regards to health, comfort and low energy bills (Interview 3), as well as decreases in air pollution (EEA, n.d.). Negative effects include the higher level of upfront investment of around 10% of total costs (Erhorn and Erhorn-Kluttig, 2018), and a grid destabilization following an increased production of renewable energies in NZEBs (Hughes and Molloy, 2022). Given the many co-benefits and little trade-offs, the success of the policy with respect to domain criteria can be considered resilient.

Subsection 5.1.4: Target groups

There is no explicit target group that the EPBD was created for, and it applies to everyone in the same way (Interview 4). Over time, the EU came to stress more that renovations can save people from energy poverty (Interview 3). However, this depends on the availability of separate funding programs. If they exist in an appropriate volume, minimum energy standards can have a redistribution effect and benefit people that face energy poverty (Interview 7, Cludius et al., 2024). However, there is frequent critique that funding schemes do not suffice to achieve the targets for renovation, or are not well targeted to reach people facing energy poverty. This way, minimum energy requirements benefit the wealthy and highly educated, as they are able to navigate the administrative burden of applying for funds (Interview 7). Further, it is likely that the costs for energy efficiency measures are to be borne by tenants, as landlords likely pass on costs to them (Interview 7; Remien, 2011). Since it is

not clear whether a target group profited from the EPBD we refrain from evaluating this indicator.

Subsection 5.1.5: Opposition to program aims

The proposal for a reform of the EPBD met some concerns from MS'. Except for Denmark, no MS was enthusiastic about the recast. Political issues in Germany and the UK kept those dominant front runners from playing a strong role in the Council, and Eastern European states were sceptical to target the existing building stock (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). MS' emphasized the subsidiarity principle, which meant that MS' should retain authority if intervention by the EU is not necessary, and criticized measures that lead to a centralization of power at the EU level. Furthermore, they demanded that for a reform, lessons from the previous EPBD 2002 should be considered first. Additionally, they criticized the proposal for making minimum standards applicable for all buildings that face major renovations, and the financial implications linked to this (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013; Dupont, 2016). This lack of support and industry pressure made even some Commission officials skeptical towards a revision of the EPBD (Boasson & Wettestad, 2013). Nevertheless, MS did not oppose the aims of the EPBD reform. In the end, the opposition from the Council and support from Parliament balanced each other out to a conflicted success.

Subsection 5.2: Process Success

Subsection 5.2.1: Preservation of policy goals and instruments

In the policy process of the EPBD 2010 at EU level, the core features that the Commission proposed in 2008 (European Commission, 2008a) remained in the final text of the policy adopted on May, 19th 2010 (Directive (EU) 2010/31). This concerns an increased focus on renewable energy sources, a template for calculating "cost-optimal" energy performance levels, and the application of minimum energy performance requirements for all buildings that undergo major renovations. However, some significant changes were made by the Council in the negotiations on the Directive with the Parliament, to prevent a centralization of authority towards the EU, and keep flexibility for implementation through the MS (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). One example is the formulation of the minimum energy standards for new buildings. The Commission in the proposal introduced "buildings of which both carbon dioxide emissions and primary energy consumption are low or equal to zero" (European Commission, 2008a). The Parliament wanted to call them "zero energy buildings", but the Council did not want to go beyond the proposal of the Commission and with the Parliament, the frame of "nearly zero energy buildings" was agreed. (Dupont, 2016). Specifications on the definition of "nearly zero energy", cost-optimal, and financing mechanisms were left open for the MS (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013; Dupont, 2016). If extending the policy process to the implementation by the MS, standards for NZEBs in MS policy processes changed further over the years before they were enforced

nationally, for example due to the different country contexts, the development of new standards, new cost-optimal reports, or the realization that some standards for renewable energy were hard to achieve in urban contexts (Erhorn-Kluttig and Erhorn, 2018b). Due to these significant changes, especially compared to the more ambitious report from the Parliament, success in this indicator can be considered as conflicted.

Subsection 5.2.2: Conferring legitimacy

The policy process that led to these changes followed the formal EU decision-making process, but the Council partly questioned the necessity of introducing stricter measures (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013; Dupont, 2016). This was overcome by tying the EPBD process to the Climate Change Conference in Copenhagen by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in 2009, so that an adoption of the EPBD recast would allow the EU to showcase their climate leadership. The Commissioner from the Directorate-General for Energy in the Commission, Peter Piebalgs, the Swedish Council presidency, and the rapporteur in the Parliament were important actors in the process that managed to create legitimacy for the policy. However, some MS' remained critical of the EPBD and showed low ambition in the transposition, so the process can only be considered a conflicted success from the perspective of conferring legitimacy.

Subsection 5.2.3: Building a sustainable coalition

The lack of legitimacy partly derives from a failure to build a sustainable coalition that supports more ambition in the EPBD, and even building a coalition for the realized small changes proved difficult. The Commission collaborated with the thermal insulation industry to create a mechanism of cost-optimality based minimum standards (Zangheri et al., 2022) intended to motivate MS' to adopt stricter and more costly regulation (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). Since the implementation of the first EPBD, lobbying groups from the insulation industry were also more supportive and actively engaged in the EPBD process (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). In the Parliament, the rapporteur on the file, Silvia-Adriana Ţicău, a Romanian Member of European Parliament from the group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D), managed to create support for a proposal that was more ambitious than that of the Council (Dupont, 2016).

Another factor that secured a sustainable coalition for the adoption of the EPBD was the initiative of the Swedish Council presidency, to prioritize the EPBD in preparation for the Climate Change conference in Copenhagen, and coordinate an agreement on the file (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013; Dupont, 2016). However, the failure to centralize more decision-making power at EU level for higher climate ambition indicates that the Commission, industry, and Parliament were not able to create enough support of their initial policy goals, particularly among actors in the Council,

which points towards a precarious success in building a sustainable coalition (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013; Dupont, 2016).

Subsection 5.3: Political Success

Subsection 5.3.1: Reputation and electoral prospects

The stakeholder consultation in 2016 found that the regulatory processes of the EPBD are mostly considered necessary (Boermans et al., 2015; European Commission, 2016b). The effects of the policy created no visible political turbulence, or consequences for electoral prospects for representatives in the Commission, Parliament, or Council. On the contrary, once it was adopted, the EPBD enabled the EU to demonstrate its aspirations for global climate leadership and probably gain some political reputation during the UNFCCC Conference in Copenhagen in 2009, even though its outcomes did not match the goals (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013).

Subsection 5.3.2: Controlling the policy agenda

There were some difficulties in managing the agenda of the EPBD 2010. Initially, there was low support for a reform of the EPBD within the Commission, so the then Commissioner for Energy, Peter Piebalgs needed some political effort to bring it on the agenda (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). Negotiations in the Council also proved difficult, but in the end the overall Commission's capacity to govern was not perturbed. After its adoption, the EPBD 2010 further indirectly eased additional steps towards climate mitigation in the building stock (Interview 3). The absence of outcomes of the EPBD on GHG emissions enabled the EU to legitimize more requirements for MS' in the upcoming EPBDs. Arguably, it took quite some time until further significant changes were implemented with the EPBD 2024, as the EPBD 2018 was a rather minor reform. However, this stalemate probably resulted from other political crisis, like the financial crisis, or the migration crisis, which slowed down overall climate policy in the EU (Rietig, 2021; Skjærseth, 2021). The significant changes of the EPBD 2024 include the Building Renovation Plans, where MS have to create detailed plans for how to decarbonize their building stock by 2050, with specific trajectories for the renovation of the existing building stock. They also include the Zero emission building standard for new buildings by 2030, that build on experiences from the NZEB requirements (Directive (EU) 2024/1275). If the building codes from the EPBD 2010 had not yet existed, such more demanding policies would have been harder to introduce.

Subsection 5.3.3: Broad values of the government and opposition against political benefits

In addition, the EPBD 2010 did not impact the broad values and direction of the Commission's work. Lastly, the EPBD 2010 was not characterized by opposition against the political benefits for the government. Overall, this makes the EPBD 2010 a resilient political success, even if its importance for the entire EU politics is rather low.

Section 6

Success of the EPBD in the Netherlands

Subsection 6.1: Program Success

Subsection 6.1.1: Meeting objectives

In the Netherlands, the objectives of the EPBD were successfully transposed, after facing an infringement procedure by the Commission in 2015 for not properly implementing the minimum requirements for major renovations and building components (van Belzen, 2015). Energy Performance Standards (EPN) for new buildings existed since 1995 and were replaced by NEN 7120 in July 2012 (NEN, 2012). They were based on the energy performance coefficient that indicates the energetic efficiency of a building (how much energy is used in a building per square meter, per year). The coefficient was at 0.8 for new residential homes (and 1.1 for offices) in 2010, and was progressively adjusted to 0.6 in 2012 and to 0.4 (and 0.8 for office buildings) in 2015 (van Cruchten, 2020). This tightening represents significant improvements in the energy requirements of new buildings. There is no indication that the standards for major renovations, building components, or technical building systems changed following the introduction of the EPBD 2010.

In 2021 with the enforcement of the NZEBs, a new calculation method was introduced in the context of the Nederlands Technische Afspraak 8800 (NTA 8800) (NEN, 2018), but the standards were not lowered further (van Cruchten, 2020; Vlot et al., 2021; Interview 1). There were also standards for buildings that undergo major renovations, as well as minor renovations that were adjusted in light of the building decree (“Bouwbesluit”) in 2012, which entered into force in 2013–2014 (Bouwbesluit, 2012; van Cruchten, 2020). These standards were scheduled to become slightly more stringent in 2021 (van Cruchten, 2021). What the Netherlands did not have was minimum energy requirements for technical building systems, but on the 10th of March 2020, standards were finally introduced (van Cruchten, 2020).

The Dutch requirements are enforced via the municipalities. A project developer must demonstrate full compliance with the standards for obtaining a building permit from the municipality. The municipality is also responsible for monitoring and enforcement during construction. Construction can be ceased until it complies again with the

standards. Every year, a sample is drawn by The Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO)¹ to check if permits are in line with legal requirements (van Cruchten, 2020; van Eck, 2015). Compliance with standards on building components and technical building systems is not being monitored (Interview 6). A report from the European Commission found a relatively low compliance rate of 57% in the Netherlands for new buildings (Jamieson et al., 2015). Overall, the implementation of the EPBD 2010 in the Netherlands had conflicted success in being in line with the objectives. While there was considerable progress until 2015, this was followed by a lack of further tightening of the standards from 2015 onwards, and a low compliance rate for new buildings.

Subsection 6.1.2: Outcomes

There are no ex-post evaluations of the specific emission reductions from the minimum energy performance standards in the Netherlands (Interview 6, Interview 8, Interview 17). Next to ex-ante assessments of the expected reductions (PBL, 2024), the trend of overall emissions in the building sector is monitored, which can give an indication for the performance of the minimum energy performance requirements.

The trends for GHG emissions and energy savings in the Dutch building sector are comparable to trends observed at the EU level. Emissions decreased from around 27 Mt in 2010 to around 24 Mt in 2020 (~11.1%), while energy consumption decreased by ~9.3% from 750 PJ in 2010 to 680 PJ in 2020 (Niessink et al., 2025; PBL, 2024; BZK, 2023). Savings from installations and insulations increased from 6 PJ/year to 8 PJ/year, and GHG emissions decreased steadily in the same period (Niessink et al., 2025; RVO, 2024). However, most emission reductions came from lower GHG emissions in the electricity mix and not from direct emissions or energy savings. There has also been a stagnation of energy consumption from 2015 onwards (Niessink et al., 2025). Interviewee 6 argues that, “the anticipated additional effect of GHG emission reductions of BENG is low, because new buildings already have very low emissions rates, and for buildings undergoing major renovations it is also low, because they don’t occur often.” (PBL, 2016). This indicates an overall precarious success in lowering GHG emissions from the building sector.

Subsection 6.1.3: Domain criteria

As negative side effects, actors from the construction sector have highlighted a rise in initial average investment costs for NZEB due to the EPBD requirements (De Leeuw, 2021a; Smit, 2021). A study commissioned by the Dutch Advisory Board on Regulatory Burden (‘Adviescollege Toetsing Regeldruk’ (ATR)) (Koning et al., 2020), also points out that the NZEB standards are not cost-optimal, and that the resulting CO₂ abatement costs are higher than for other policy measures (Koning et al., 2020). However, this

¹ The Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO) helps entrepreneurs and organisations to invest, develop and expand their businesses and projects both in the Netherlands and abroad. RVO is a government agency which is part of the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs.

stands in contrast to numerous other Dutch cost-optimality studies that served as a basis to determining the minimum energy performance standards (Peppelman, 2018; van Eck, 2015; van Cruchten, 2020; Daniëls and Koelemeijer, 2016; De Leeuw, 2021b). Other construction actors confirm that the NZEB-related cost increases are considered manageable, and smaller in comparison to additional costs caused by another national regulation regarding phasing-out of gas boilers (Interview 14; Interview 15; Interview 16).

In the Netherlands, there has been some critique on the regulatory burden and the complexity of the new energy performance calculation method (NTA 8800) (Kromhof, 2021; Vlot et al., 2021; Dit hele circus, 2021; Interview 1). Previously, the energy performance had to be calculated on paper for the whole building, but now an individual calculation for every apartment is necessary. Once the construction plans turn out infeasible in the construction, and solutions that differ from the plans are implemented, this can change the calculation. Moreover, there are unrealistic assumptions about energy performance on which the calculation is based. This complexity results in extra time needed for constructors, makes building more expensive, and complicates the communication of energy-efficiency related performance improvements of buildings to stakeholders. Following this critique, the requirements for the calculation of individual energy labels were removed (De Leeuw, 2023). On the other hand, municipalities reported that the new calculation method made processing of building permits easier and quicker (Interview 10).

There are further co-benefits and negative side effects that result from the implementation of the EPBD in the Netherlands. While the construction rates of new buildings remained stable, the issuing of permits has fallen since the introduction of NTA 8800 in 2021 (RVO, 2024), but this is more likely due to a national housing crisis, and additional rising costs of construction originating from energy crisis, supply chain crisis, and inflation. Nevertheless, before adopting BENG, a decision was made to make the BENG requirements less ambitious because of a potential goal conflict with the number of newbuilt homes (Interview 8). There have been reports on delays in construction, among other things resulting from a lack of certified advisors (Vlot et al., 2021). On the positive side, the EPBD 2010 brought an increased focus on renewable energies in buildings. For example, an increase of geothermal heat installations can be observed, starting from 2017 (RVO, 2024; Niessink et al., 2025). The installation of solar panels on buildings has also benefitted from this increased focus, but in turn contributed to net congestion problems (Interview 1; Vlot et al., 2021). Further, energy efficiency measures have been disadvantaged in the NTA 8800 compared with the previous NEN 7120, and it has been reported that BENG conflicts with circularity goals (Interview 9). Overall, this indicates a conflicted success of domain criteria in the Dutch case.

Subsection 6.1.4: Target groups

BENG further failed to benefit the target group of the insulation industry, which complained that the new BENG requirements in the NTA 8800 have disadvantaged insulation as compared to renewable energy (van Belzen, 2019; Niessink et al., 2025). This indicates a conflicted success, next to the benefits towards the renewable energy sector, although evidence on the benefits for specific target groups is generally scarce, similar to the case of the EU.

Subsection 6.1.5: Opposition to program aims

In the Netherlands, opposition towards the aims of the building codes focused on a few different points. First, the complexity of the new NTA 8800 standard was criticized by construction and installation companies ('Dit hele circus', 2021), and by tenant organizations (Woonbond, 2019). Second, the BENG requirement on energy efficiency was a focus of critique. Some construction actors opposed the requirements on energy efficiency of BENG (Vlot et al., 2021; Interview 14). In contrast, the insulation industry complained that insulation was disadvantaged compared to (renewable energy-based) heat installations and solar panels, considering previous regulation (van Belzen, 2019). The Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO) and tenant associations shared this critique and advised higher insulation requirements (van Belzen, 2019; Woonbond, 2019). Another line of critique focused on the split incentive of renovation for landlords and tenants following from BENG. The argumentation of housing associations here is that while landlords need to make the investment for efficiency measures, it is tenants who profit from lower energy bills (Aedes et al., 2019). At the same time tenant organizations warned about potential negative effects on the affordability and fairness of housing, especially for low-income tenants (Woonbond, 2019). Although more fundamental disagreements between the values of construction speed, cost-efficiency and insulation also existed (van Belzen, 2019; Interview 6), opposition in the Dutch case led only to smaller adjustments on details, and was overall outweighed by support, indicating a resilient success.

Subsection 6.2: Process Success

Subsection 6.2.1: Preservation of policy goals and instruments

For the alterations of the Energy performance standards for buildings (NEN 7120) between 2010 and 2015, as well as alterations for major renovations, building components, or technical building systems in the Bouwbesluit, there is no evidence that the Dutch government needed to compromise on their initial goals. On the contrary, for the NTA 8800, some alterations have been made from the first preliminary version of this standard from 2015. In 2018, the requirements for the energy demand (BENG 1) for residential buildings were relaxed from 25 kWh/m² per year to 70

kWh/m² per year (Lente Akkoord 2.0, n.d., Interview 17). This followed a new cost-optimality study (Peppelman, 2018) and critique from societal actors (van Belzen, 2019) that the earlier requirements were not cost-efficient (BouwTotaal, 2018). This relaxation in turn earned critique from the insulation industry and in 2019 then, BENG 1 was tightened again to 55 kWh/m² per year, following further refinements from a public consultation (BouwTotaal, 2021). In the end, despite the introduction of NTA 8800, climate ambition remained unchanged in these standards compared to the old NEN 7120 standard (van Cruchten, 2020; Vlot et al., 2021; Interview 1). Given this stagnation of the minimum energy standards since 2015, and the failure to keep the initially envisaged tighter standards, this can be considered a conflicted success to preserve policy goals and instruments.

Subsection 6.2.2: Conferring legitimacy

The policymaking procedures in the Dutch case followed standard approaches, and in combination with the cost-optimality studies the process created legitimacy for the introduction of new standards (Interview 6). Moreover, it can be noted that the reference to the obligation to implement this EU legislation is used to create legitimacy (Interview 8). However, when the cost-optimality studies suggested low values for BENG requirements, it was hard to legitimize action beyond what is cost-efficient, although it might be required to reach climate targets. Given this dilemma, the process had conflicted success to confer legitimacy to more climate ambition.

Subsection 6.2.3: Building a sustainable coalition

The policy process in the Dutch case was based on a large stakeholder consultation from 2013, the national Energy Agreement (“Energie Akkoord”). The result of this consultation was an agreement among 40 participants and other stakeholders for targets on energy efficiency improvements and the use of renewable energy sources (RES) in buildings (van Cruchten, 2020). Moreover, in the design process of the NTA 8800, RVO consulted construction companies, insulation companies, municipalities and consumer organizations to secure support of a large coalition of actors (‘Dit hele circus’, 2021, Interview 8, Interview 14). On one hand, these participatory initiatives secured legitimacy for the change of the calculation method from NEN 7120 to NTA 8800, but on the other hand they did not result in higher standards than before (Interview 17). Again, this represents a conflicted success of the process in building a sustainable coalition.

Subsection 6.3: Political Success

Subsection 6.3.1: Reputation and electoral prospects

There is no indication that the Dutch implementation of the EPBD at any time influenced electoral prospects. However, from the hesitation to introduce a tightening of standards for the NTA 8800, it can be assumed that the government was not willing to take a political risk (Interview 17) and was potentially concerned about reputational impacts. This might be connected to experiences of opposition towards the tightening of standards from the energy performance coefficient of 0.8 to 0.4 for residential homes that occurred between 2010 and 2015 and followed pressure from Brussels to implement the EPBD (van Belzen, 2015). This potential impact on political reputation in the years up to 2015, and the political success of climate inaction in the NTA 8800 process result in an overall conflicted reputational success.

Subsection 6.3.2: Controlling the policy agenda and broad values of the government

The successful policy processes generally enabled the government to follow their agenda without disturbance. An exception is the introduction of the NTA 8800, which was more controversial than expected with regards to its complexity, and needed some political calibrations (Vlot et al., 2021; 'Dit hele circus', 2021; De Leeuw, 2023). Nevertheless, there are no signs, that the EPBD implementation had effects on the broader values and direction of government in the buildings domain. The subsequent introduction of mandatory energy performance for existing office buildings is an example of how the Dutch government continued to push for innovative policies for climate mitigation in buildings in an EU context (Eichholtz et al., 2024). Overall, the implementation of the EPBD was a resilient success in terms of the agenda and broader values and direction of the government.

Section 7

Success of the EPBD in Germany

Subsection 7.1: Program Success

Subsection 7.1.1: Meeting objectives

In Germany, the objectives of the EPBD 2010 were largely met (Schettler-Köhler, 2021), but did not cause much additional ambition (Interview 4; Clausen and Beucker, 2020). The EnEV already contained minimum requirements for building components and technical building systems. The EnEV was reformed in 2013 to include small changes necessary to implement the EPBD 2010 (Howard and Rosenberger, 2020; Schettler-Köhler and Ahlke, 2018). This did not include alterations to existing standards for major renovations (Interview 2, Interview 5). The NZEB standards were lowered by 25%, starting from 2016 onward (Interview 4), but were not subsequently altered until the NZEB enforcement in the context of the adoption of the GEG in 2020. After the official enforcement of the NZEB regulation, and after a change of government in 2022, NZEB standards were lowered by another 20% (Interview 4).

The enforcement of the national regulations in Germany is carried out by the federal states, which have varying practices for how strictly the rules are enforced (Howard and Rosenberger, 2020; Interviews 2 and 4). They report their experiences with the energy performance requirements in the building permits to the federal government, but those reports are not accessible to the public (Interview 2). For building components and technical building systems, it is hard to tell what their impact is, because it is not being monitored how many of these minor renovations are implemented (Interviews 2). Non-compliance with building code regulations in Germany was estimated at 25%, where lack of personnel at the federal level was seen as the main reason contributing to this (Edmondson et al., 2024). If non-compliance is discovered, fines can be issued ("Missachten der EnEV", 2014). For new buildings, and for technical building systems, compliance with standards was deemed largely given due to liability issues for craftspeople, but for renovations compliance rates were more questionable because there were no controls and (formal) evaluations were performed (Interviews 2, 4, 5; Clausen and Beucker, 2020). Stricter enforcement measures have been discussed within government in the context of the introduction of the GEG in 2020, but were never approved (Bauchmüller, 2012b). The success of

implementation is thus conflicted. On the one hand, there were significant alterations of the standards for new buildings, but also delays, and no alterations for renovations, building components, or technical buildings systems. A gap in compliance and enforcement adds to this picture.

Subsection 7.1.2: Outcomes

The outcomes of the EPBD implementation in Germany are not subject to formal or governmental evaluation processes, similar to the EU and the Netherlands. There are ex-ante projections, but they are not complemented by ex-post analyses. “[T]he estimation of what effect a tightening of regulatory law will have on emissions in the long term is all very, very model-based and assumption-driven. There is simply no data on this.” (Edmondson et al., 2024; Interview 4, Interview 5). “It is simply that in the end everyone more or less takes a stab in the dark of their expectations” (Interview 2).

The overall trend of GHG emission reductions in the German building sector can give an indication of the effectiveness of the EPBD. The trend follows the same pattern as in the EU and the Netherlands. Decreasing emissions are mainly due to indirect emissions, while direct emissions did only slightly decrease since 2010 and roughly remained at the same level of around 120 Mt CO₂ equivalents since 2014, with the exception for 2022 and 2023 caused by the energy crisis (Dena, 2024). The consumption of energy in buildings even slightly increased between 2014 and 2021, from ~625 TWh to ~700TWh, which was mainly due to increasing demand in space heating (Dena, 2024; Interview 2). Nevertheless, “the standards for new buildings prevented negative outliers and together with subsidies helped realizing very efficient buildings. They did help to increase a focus on renewable energies in new buildings” (Interview 5), but they did not trigger much additional efforts in terms of energy efficiency (Interview 4). This also showcases a precarious success in the outcomes of the EPBD in Germany.

Subsection 7.1.3: Domain criteria

The German requirements within the EnEV 2013 are generally considered to be cost optimal (Howard and Rosenberger, 2020; Interview 5), although a study from the Ministry for Transport, Building and Urban Development concluded that the 25% reduction are not cost effective (Ochs, 2013a). On the contrary, critique also existed that the assumptions of the cost-optimality study were too pessimistic and higher standards could have also been cost-efficient (Interview 2). Similar to the Netherlands, some actors emphasized the necessary additional investment costs for new buildings and potential rent increases (Ochs, 2013a; Ochs, 2013b; Vetter, 2015). Some conclude that these costs are amortized by the energy savings (Rose, 2020b), while others negated that (Remien, 2015; Diermann, 2018b). One study even finds that it would be more efficient to renovate more buildings to lower standards than to renovate at the current standards (Galvin, 2023). Rose and Lorenz-Göckes (2021)

highlight that the consideration of individual houses in the minimum requirements is not efficient compared to neighborhood approaches. Finally, it is worth noting that cost-effectiveness is not always considered the best guiding principle, and it is not confirmed that the necessary actions to reach climate targets are all cost-efficient (Interview 4; Rose, 2020a). For example, while thermal insulation is less cost-effective than substituting fossil boilers, it is still needed, because there are limits to energy availability, and technical reasons to improve the efficiency of a heat pump.

Administrative and fiscal burdens are deemed minimal, as there are no additional efforts for the implementation and enforcement of the EPBD (Interview 4). Potentially, higher standards could even lead to higher tax income, because of the increase in construction activity (Interview 4). There are negative side-effects of the EPBD implementation insofar insulation material creates a waste problem (Hoffmann, 2023). The number of constructions of new buildings and the issuing of building permits has not changed after the EnEV 2013, but declined since 2020 likely due to the same external factors as the ones observed in the Dutch case, and do not result from the introduction of higher standards in the GEG in 2022 (Dena, 2024). A study on the effects of the EnEV on construction costs found that it probably increased construction costs, but that this effect is spread over several years and is overlain by other effects. Still, there is a probable slight setback of constructed buildings (Dorffmeister and Kocijan, 2016). As a co-benefit, reinforced employment of craft persons is mentioned (Interview 4). Overall, the domain criteria represent a resilient success of the policy.

Subsection 7.1.4: Target groups

With regards to effects on target groups, it has been reported that renovations can contribute to gentrification, when tenants cannot afford an increased rent after renovation (Diermann, 2016). There are however no systematic studies on the distributional effects of the EnEV/GEG (Interview 5). It should also be noted that the EPBD does not provoke mandatory actions in itself, but only applies if the decision to build or renovate a building is being taken (Interview 2). The construction sector is seen as a profiteer concerning the increase in construction and renovation activity (Interview 3, Interview 7; Dorffmeister and Kocijan, 2016), with the thermal insulation industry involved in lobbying for a revision (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013). Another possible benefitting group are building owners that fulfil the EnEV criteria. They benefit from increased property values, higher rent, and lower marketing costs (Günther, 2012). Due to a lack of analysis on benefitting actors, we did not assess this category for Germany.

Subsection 7.1.5: Opposition to program aims

In the German case, opposition to readjustments of the minimum standards for the EnEV 2013 originates largely from construction and real estate agents. The critique mainly concerns questions of cost-effectiveness and that higher standards will increase construction costs more than what can be earned back by the energy savings. Instead, they propose to alter the funds for renovation of existing buildings (Rose, 2011; Steinhauer, 2011; Remien, 2011; Diermann, 2012; Ochs, 2013a; Ochs, 2013b; Rose, 2013; Remien 2015). They also point out that the construction of inexpensive apartments is not feasible with new standards (Gericke, 2013; Vetter, 2015). Real estate actors also questioned the potential for energy savings, and demand cost savings through deregulation (Rose, 2012). They also suggest that it would be better to renovate many buildings to a lower standard, than to renovate a few buildings to high standards (Lange, 2011). On the contrary, environmental associations demanded stricter standards and a plan for renovations in the EnEV (Dapd, 2012). In the end, standards were increased in 2016 for new buildings, but not for the renovation of existing buildings.

Subsequently, there were discussions to alter the standard for new buildings again in the context of discussions on the new GEG. Real estate and construction actors were still against these higher standards (Rose, 2017; Zweifel an Wirtschaftlichkeit von Passivhäusern, 2016; Diermann, 2018b; Clausen and Beucker, 2020), and protested the “chaos” of many reforms and questioned the efficiency of the EnEV regulations (Diermann, 2016). To increase cost efficiency, they suggested to focus less on individual buildings, but instead pursue a neighbourhood approach (Rose and Lorenz-Göckes 2021). The construction and real estate actors this time were able to convince conservatives in the government to first delay the reform for the elections in 2017 (Diermann, 2018a), and subsequently to not introduce higher standards. This met opposition from researchers, stressing that they are needed in order to meet the climate goals (Rose, 2020a). Furthermore, environmental associations demanded stricter standards and a plan for renovations (Clausen and Beucker, 2020). Energy associations were less critical about that, but criticized the lack of integration of district heating and biogas (Clausen and Beucker, 2020). There were also concerns about that the regulations favours synthetic materials and creates a waste problem, although announced by the brick industry that has a vested interest in promoting more traditional insulation through bricks (Hoffmann, 2023). Overall, in the German case opposition is balanced between less opposition for the EnEV reform, and more opposition for the GEG legislation, leading to conflicted levels of success for this indicator.

Subsection 7.2: Process Success

Subsection 7.2.1: Preservation of policy goals and instruments

In Germany, three policy processes to alter the minimum standards occurred since the introduction of the EPBD 2010, with different success in preserving the initial policy goals. First, in the context of the first reform of the EnEV 2013, a 25% reduction of the requirements for new buildings was adopted, but standards for existing buildings, building components and technical systems remained the same (Rose, 2013; Schettler-Köhler, 2021). This represents a higher ambition than the 7.5% that were suggested by the responsible ministries in 2012 (Bauchmüller, 2012a), but it represents a lower ambition than previously formulated goals of reducing energy use in buildings by up to 30 percent (Diermann, 2012).

Second, there was a ministerial draft for a new act (the GEG) in 2016 that included the EnEV and proposed to alter the KfW-70 standard to a KfW 55 standard for non-residential public buildings (Rose, 2017; Diermann, 2017; Schettler-Köhler and Ahlke, 2018). However, in the developing political discussions there were concerns that this alteration of standard would indicate a potential new standard for residential NZEBs for 2021, and this was perceived as politically sensitive in light of the upcoming elections in 2017. Ultimately, a group of MPs from the coalition reached an adjournment until the next legislative period from 2017-2021 (Schettler-Köhler, 2021). In the end, the GEG was adopted in 2020, and the NZEB standard was defined at the old level of KfW-70 (Ochs, 2019; Clausen and Beucker, 2020; Rose, 2020a; Schettler-Köhler, 2021). Thus, for this reform, the government faced major delays and did not manage to preserve their own goals, which equals a policy failure.

Third, the government of Christian democrats (CDU/CSU) and social democrats (SPD) was replaced in 2021 by a new government, consisting of social democrats (SPD), greens, and liberals (FDP). This new government immediately introduced the KfW-55 standard for residential buildings (Interview 4), which underlines the failure of the previous government to preserve their own initial policy goals of altering the standard for non-residential buildings to the KfW-55 standard. Overall, the difficulties and delays in the process can be considered a precarious success of preserving initial policy goals.

Subsection 7.2.2: Conferring legitimacy

In all of these processes, standard policymaking procedures were followed, and cost-optimality studies were published accordingly, both creating legitimacy for the introduction of new standards (Interview 5; Interview 6). However, the inability to introduce higher standards, and the delay in adopting the GEG indicates a lack of ability of the process to confer legitimacy for higher standards.

Subsection 7.2.3: Building a sustainable coalition

While the adoption of the EnEV 2013 indicates a somewhat stable coalition of actors that supported higher standards, in the subsequent process the government did not show enough political will to create support from actors for further tightening. The positions of prevalent actors did not change much during the German transposition of the EPBD, from EnEV 2013, to GEG 2020 (Interview 2). While environmental actors were found to generally support stricter standards, tenant associations position themselves ambivalently, and real estate and construction actors rather oppose them. The failure of the German GEG reform in 2017 visualizes that the process was not able to generate the necessary support among relevant actors, such as real estate actors and the federal states (Rose, 2017; Diermann, 2017). However, the new government in 2022 managed to get enough support from actors for the further tightening of the standards for new buildings. This culminates in an overall conflicted success to build a sustainable coalition of actors.

Subsection 7.3: Political Success

Subsection 7.3.1: Reputation and electoral prospects

In Germany, the introduction of the EnEV 2013 created quite a public outcry (Interview 5; Rose, 2012; Ochs, 2013a; Remien, 2015). This had an effect on subsequent decision-making. The failure to create a GEG reform in the legislative period 2013–2017 results from anticipated negative political effects from such a policy (Interview 5). It was feared that higher minimum energy performance standards for buildings would bring up accusations of making housing more expensive, which the government wanted to avoid in the upcoming electoral campaigns (Rose, 2017). The EPBD implementation in Germany with regards to reputation is therefore a precarious success.

Subsection 7.3.2: Controlling the policy agenda and broad values of the government

After the EnEV 2013, no further strengthening of building codes were planned. Instead, funding for renovations were intended to be increased and simplified, but only if there is financial leeway (Diermann, 2013; Interview 5). While this might indicate that the government was not able to maintain the agenda of making buildings more efficient, it can also be attributed to trying to prevent too much regulatory changes, that have in turn be translated into new funding programs and standards (Interview 5). Nevertheless, the introduction of EnEV raised the issue of construction costs on the agenda, which was prominent in the legislative period 2013–2017 after the EnEV (Schettler-Köhler, 2021). These events demonstrate that the EnEV proved more controversial and took more political resources than anticipated. While the broad direction of the government was still in favour of climate mitigation in buildings, some

rethinking is visible with the shift of emphasis on funding schemes instead of mandatory standards, as well as the higher importance of construction costs, compared to climate mitigation. Overall, this represents a conflicted political success of the EnEV.

Subsequently, the first failed attempt to reform the GEG in 2017 showcases that even reinforcing the standards for public non-residential buildings, which is considered a minor change, proved more controversial than expected and took up more political time and resources than expected (Schettler-Köhler, 2021; Diermann, 2018a). For the finally adopted reform of the GEG in 2020 then, the failure to introduce higher minimum energy performance standards contributed to the general image of the failure of the government on climate policy (Grzanna, 2021). In the campaign for the federal elections in 2021, the government parties adapted more climate change mitigation framing in their electoral campaigns, which represents again a rethinking and significant change of political direction on the issue. Ultimately, the government was voted out in the federal elections in 2021, and the new government rapidly introduced higher standards in 2022. In summary, for the political success of the GEG reform, the inaction of the government first proved politically successful, but later ended in compromising the entire trajectory of government with its electoral defeat in 2021. This marks a precarious success, so that overall the political success of the GEG levels out to a conflicted success. Finally, considering the conflicted success of the EnEV, the overall political success of the EPBD implementation in Germany is therefore conflicted.

Table 5: Overview over the success of the EPBD implementation in the three cases and dimensions of success

Success dimension	EU	NL	GER
Process	Conflicted success	Resilient success	Conflicted success
Program	Precarious success	Precarious success	Precarious success
Politics	Resilient Success	Resilient success	Conflicted success

Section 8

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study determined the success of the building codes from the EPBD 2010 with regards to process, program, and political outcomes. The results of this study show that while the EPBD is effective in preventing sub-optimal energy efficiency of buildings, it contributed only to a small extent to GHG emission reductions in the buildings sector. This is because the EPBD 2010 has regulated only a small part of the building stock, targeting mainly new buildings, and planned renovations. The lack of ambition derives from a conflicted process that followed regular procedures, but failed to realize support for more ambition from crucial actors, such as the Council, or national construction and real estate industries. A better collaboration with those actors in the policy process could potentially enable more ambition in the EPBD. It might also prevent subsequent political consequences, as observed in the German case, where the government struggled to introduce subsequent legislation on energy efficiency in buildings after the alteration of minimum energy requirements following the EPBD 2010. To conclude, the case of the EPBD illustrates how a lack of process success can impede outcomes of the policy, but also political outcomes.

Subsection 8.1: Comparison of cases and success dimensions

Another aim this study set out with was a comparison of the success of the EPBD between EU and national levels. On the process level, the Netherlands stand out with slightly more successful processes that emphasize the participation of stakeholders, and consensus-orientation, which creates legitimacy for the policy output and largely achieved the goals that government initially formulated. The processes of the EU and Germany, whereas are more conflicted successes. The EU was not able to introduce some of the Parliament's initial goals of "zero energy buildings", specific definitions and financial measures. However, it was more successful in legitimizing the adoption of a EPBD reform through an innovative collaboration with the insulation industry that created the "cost-optimal" mechanism. While the German case showcases two successful processes, where the then governments managed to tighten standards, for a long time it failed to show the political will to legitimize and build a coalition for higher standards.

The program success is precarious in all three cases, because the GHG emission trends in the building sector indicate only a small reduction of GHG emission reductions, and therefore low effect of the EPBD on overall emissions. This is underlined by stagnant direct emissions, and energy consumption since 2015 in all cases. The implementation of the EPBD has broadly met the objectives, but there is a compliance gap and lack of harmonization. The Netherlands has not elevated the standards since 2015, and Germany has only accomplished that after a long political struggle. There are generally many co-benefits, and fewer trade-offs in all cases. Standards are usually cost-effective, create little administrative and regulatory burden, and co-benefits for renewable energies. However, in the Netherlands, this contributed to net congestion, and came at the expense of co-benefits for insulation, therefore benefitting the renewable energy industry and disadvantaging the insulation industry. There is a lack of analyses on the benefits for target groups. While opposition to the program aims in the Netherlands was overall outweighed by support, at EU level and in Germany, opposition and support balanced each other out. At EU level, opposition came from MS', and support from Parliament, and in Germany it was divided between real estate and construction actors on one side and environmental actors, as well as renewable and insulation industries on the other hand.

Politically, the EPBD represents a resilient success for the EU and Netherlands, and a conflicted success for Germany. While the EU gained from an increase in climate leadership reputation, the reputational impacts of the tightening of the standards for the Dutch and German government proved more controversial, albeit with different political outcomes. The successful processes in the Netherlands led to a still overall successful outcome and mitigated complexity issues of the new calculation method NTA 8800, with no effects on the broader values and direction of government. In Germany the intense debates on the EnEV led to a shift in government values from minimum energy performance standards to renovation funding and construction costs in the GEG process. Initially, this climate inaction proved successful, but then in turn led to precarious success and change of the political direction of government with the electoral defeat of government in 2021.

Some variations between the cases can be observed. In the process dimension, the Netherlands stands out with a more resilient success compared to the conflicted success of the EU and Germany. What seems striking in the Dutch case is the emphasis on inclusive policy processes that allow for the participation of all relevant stakeholders. While such processes also exist in Germany and at the EU level, there is less explicit emphasis on them for a successful process, and this might have contributed to overall more successful processes in the Netherlands.

In the political dimension, Germany stands out with a more conflicted success, compared to the resilient successes of the EU and the Netherlands. Compared to the Netherlands, there is more emphasis on conflict between environmental and industry actors in the public debate and this potentially reaches into governmental politics.

The inaction on the standards since 2015 existed also in the Netherlands, but this did not contribute to an overall perception of the climate inaction of the government, and a change of direction in government. In the program dimension, although all countries showcase precarious success, there are some nuances. Germany for example has tighter standards for new buildings than the Netherlands, and has more recent reforms than the Netherlands. The conflicted success of the process and political dimensions might be traced back to this ambition to push for higher standards.

Subsection 8.2: Implications for future EPBD reforms

Our findings have some implications for the creation of future EPBDs. First, there is very little evaluation on the effectiveness of the minimum energy performance standards, so the precise effects of the EPBD are not known. Conducting such ex-post evaluations could help clarifying the contribution of the EPBD to the reduction of GHG emissions in the buildings sector, and it could point to ineffectiveness that then could be addressed. It would also allow an assessment of whether ex-ante evaluations were correct, or whether their assumptions must be revised to anticipate emissions trajectories more accurately for future policy reforms.

Second, our study indicates limited effects of the EPBD on GHG emission reductions in the buildings sector. This puts existing ex-post evaluations of building codes into perspective. While, for example, El-Saghi et al. (2017), have found that pre-EPBD building codes in Germany were effective in implementing energy savings, especially for the “low-quality housing market”, we nuance that in the context of the whole building sector these gains are marginal. Thus, our study points to a need of an increased focus of regulatory policies on the renovation of existing buildings. The EPBD 2010 regulates only a small portion of the building stock, including new buildings, and major and minor renovations. All other buildings, for which there are no plans to renovate, essentially do not contribute to climate change mitigation in the sector and require policy action to ensure a fair distribution of the efforts towards decarbonization. This has been introduced with the most recent EPBD, but it still falls short of the required action (Huber et al., 2025). Our evaluation also highlights that such mandatory renovations need to be accompanied by targeted funding for vulnerable households, and overcome split incentives.

In order to improve the effectiveness of policy reforms, attention needs to be shed on policy processes. They need to be designed to better enable support from the Council for new policy proposals. One potential solution might be to develop policy ideas in the Commission with more collaboration of the Council in early stages to address concerns, for example, about centralization of decision making in a proactive way. This collaboration might also enable learning processes about previous implementation processes and national challenges, which might benefit the process

and political success of future EU transpositions, and thus ultimately the legitimacy of EU integration.

Another implication from our findings is the importance of political leadership for the success of the EPBD. The examples of the Commissioner Peter Piebalgs, the Parliamentary Rapporteur, and the Swedish Council Presidency show how individual actors are crucial for enabling the necessary support to adopt a policy and to make processes successful, as well as deal with the political consequences of a policy.

Subsection 8.3: Implications for holistic ex-ante evaluations

Finally, our findings have implications for the creation of frameworks for the holistic evaluation of climate policies. The lack of ex-post evaluations represents the situation in other policy domains in the EU, where in 2011 less than 10% of the evaluations were ex-post (Hildén et al., 2014). However, more ex-post evaluations are needed to understand the real effects of policies and improve ex-ante assessments accordingly. For example, the EU building climate tracker from BPIE (Amarocho et al., 2024) highlighted a gap between actual emission trends and what was modelled in the impact assessment from 2008. Such insights could then allow for more precise scenarios, and a realization that more climate policy action is needed to account for this gap.

More specific implications of our analysis relate to the complexity of factors that are important to understand the success of climate policies. One dimension of factors concerns the programmatic effects, which encompasses factors beyond the reduction of GHG emissions, energy consumption, and the criteria of cost-effectiveness, which are assessed in current evaluations (European Commission, 2016b). Additional relevant factors include the consideration of social justice for the distribution of benefits of the policy among the affected population. They also include behavioural insights, to better account for a performance gap in the actual use of energy after implementation of efficiency measures that are often levelled out by rebound effects and the differences of energy use along demographics of age, gender, and so forth. These may be included in the macroeconomic models, or as complementary categories in evaluation frameworks that require simultaneous qualitative analysis.

Another dimension of factors concerns the process success, which can determine the success of the outcomes of the policy. An ex-post analysis of this dimension can identify shortcomings in legitimacy, or innovativeness, or the inclusion of actors. For example, our analysis found that the Council was crucial for the (lack of) ambition in the EPBD. This insight then can help future policy reforms to find better ways to garner support from key actors for a successful adoption of the policy. Likewise, the perception of legitimacy, or innovativeness of the policy could be improved this way,

and it could be clarified whether modelling is integrated in a productive way in the policy process.

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APPENDIX 2: Interview guideline

Context EPBD 2010

To what extent was the (national implementation of) EPBD 2010 innovative (in the national context)?

How has EPBD been evaluated so far?

Overall evaluation EPBD 2010

To what extent are the building codes resulting from the implementation of the EPBD a successful policy, or a failed policy?

Programmatic dimension

To what extent did the building codes achieve a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions/ energy use?

What were the distributional effects of the building codes?

To what extent is the policy cost-effective?

What are other positive co-benefits resulting from the policy?

To what extent does the policy create fiscal burden or other negative side effects?

Process dimension

To what extent was the process of formulating and adopting the building codes successful or a failure?

To what extent did the government adopt and implement the goals and instruments it initially wanted to adopt?

To what extent was the process considered legitimate (or not)?

To what extent did the process manage to build a coalition that supports the building codes?

To what extent was the process of policymaking innovative?

How did that help the success of the policy?

Politics

To what extent did the process and outcome of the EPBD 2010 have political consequences for the government and politicians in it?

How did it impact their reputation?

How did it impact their electoral prospects?

How was the social acceptance for the policy among the population, firms and other political actors?

To what extent did this policy allow the government to control the policy agenda and ease the business of governing?

To what extent did this policy promote the values desired by government, and the trajectories of their programs?

How are these effects of the policy similar or different to the prediction of effects in ex-ante policy impact assessments?

National policy processes (GER/NL)

To what extent were the provisions of the EPBD new and required additional efforts?

How were they adopted in national legislation?

In which policies are they included?

When did these processes happen?

What is their policy design?

APPENDIX 3: Coding scheme

Table 6: Coding scheme

CODE (GROUP)	DESCRIPTION	EXAMPLE QUOTATIONS
<i>Programmatic Success</i>	<i>Attainment of the intended policy goals</i>	
Objectives	Implementation of the objectives of the policy	The report reveals that currently 25 Member States have in force a complete Nearly Zero Energy Building definition. NZEB requirements are currently 70% lower than the national minimum energy performance requirements in 2006 showing a consistent trend in increasing building energy efficiency. (Zangheri et. al, 2021)
Outcomes	Achievement of desired real-world impacts (emission reductions, energy use reductions, interaction effects)	Although saving potential remains high (Annex 7), positive effects of the EPBD are observed as follow (Annex 9). Up to 2014, 48.9 Mtoe energy savings have been achieved in total: 41.4 Mtoe in the residential sector (of which 36.6 Mtoe for space heating only), 7.5 Mtoe in the service sector. (European Commission, 2016b)
Target group	Creation of benefits for the target group and fairness, distributional effects	Of course, it has a lot of social impact and that's maybe another aspect I wanted to highlight, the social impact of the EPPD. It's um. It's amazing because we have done a work on the social impact of a different mitigation policy in energy and the only one that is possibly progressive is energy efficiency in buildings. But the problem is always the financing of these actions and the difficulties for the lowest income group to finance this this option and even in countries where 100% of the cost. Was covered by

		<p>the government. And in many cases, it's it was not well targeted, but what we see it's that it's not the one and the more in need of money that is that are benefiting it, it's the one that are the most agile with administrative burden. (Interview 7)</p>
Domain criteria	<p>Other criteria that are important for policies in the building sector, e.g. cost effectiveness, fiscal burden, co-benefits and trade-offs, transformative potential</p>	<p>Für Heizung und Belüftung müssen Bauherren heute gut acht Prozent des Budgets einplanen, im Jahr 2000 lag ihr Anteil an den Bauwerkskosten nur bei 3,7 Prozent. Große Sprünge zeigt der Index der ARGE im Zeitverlauf daher vor allem nach den Novellierungen der Energieeinsparverordnung (EnEV), die das maßgebliche Instrument der Bundesregierung für das Erreichen der klimapolitischen Ziele ist (Remien, 2015).</p> <p>Translation: Nowadays, investors must allocate 8% of the total construction budget for the purpose of heating and ventilation. Back in 2000 this ratio was at 3.7%. According to the ARGE study, alterations of this ratio are observable particularly after reforms of the Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV), which is the main instrument of the federal government to reach climate targets. (Remien, 2015)</p>
Opposition aims	<p>opposition to program aims, values and means of achieving them</p>	<p>André Meester behartigt de belangen van de Nederlandse Isolatie Industrie (NII). Hij vindt dat de isolatiebranche er in de BENG bekaaid vanaf komt. "Met de BENG die er nu ligt heb je haast 'superwarmtepompen' nodig en onnodig veel zonnepanelen. Dat komt omdat de eisen voor energiebehoefte niet streng genoeg zijn. Dat is niet effectief. Dit is een stap terug, in plaats van vooruit." (van Belzen, 2019)</p> <p>Translation: André Meester safeguards the interests of the Dutch Insulation Industry (NII). He finds that the insulation industry is being disadvantaged by the BENG requirements. "According to the current BENG, you need super heat pumps and an unnecessary number of solar panels. This is because the requirements for energy demand are not strict enough. That is not effective. It is a step backward, instead of forward." (van Belzen, 2019)</p>

<i>Process Success</i>	<i>Policymaking and implementation processes</i>	
Preservation Policy	Preservation of the initial policy goals of the government agenda	The core features were in line with the original proposal from the Commission, although some significant changes had been made. The Parliament had managed to get the national governments to accept 2018 as zero-energy deadline for the public sector, with 2020 as a deadline for new buildings in general. However, the Parliament's 'zero-energy building' wording was replaced by the far more ambiguous 'nearly zero energy buildings'. (Boasson and Wettestad, 2013)
Legitimacy	Conferral of legitimacy for the policy through the process	Member states in the Council were less enthusiastic about strengthening the Commission's proposal for a recast, and there were early indications of reticence in applying minimum standards to all buildings undergoing major renovations – a major element of the Commission's proposal. (Dupont, 2016).
Coalition	Process enables support for the policy by a sustainable coalition	Within the Council, the main pro-climate stakeholder involved in the policymaking process can perhaps be identified as the Presidency at the time of the final negotiations – Sweden (in the second half of 2009). The environmental Council was not involved, but the general green credentials of Sweden (Lieverink, Arts, Kamstra and Ooijevaar, 2009) might have helped push the dossier through. Although the official agreement on the dossier did not come until the publication of the Council's common position in April 2010 and the Parliament's adoption of this position in second reading, the negotiations in trilogues in the late part of 2009 meant that an informal agreement had been reached already in December 2009 – in time for the important round of international climate negotiations in Copenhagen. This was considered a success for the Swedish Presidency (Dupont, 2016).

Opposition process	Opposition against the design of the policy process	No quotations
<i>Political Success</i>	<i>Interactions of actors and interests in policymaking arenas</i>	
Reputation	Impacts of the policy on electoral prospect or reputation of the government, e.g. acceptance among population, firms and political actors	<p>Vor diesem Hintergrund kam in der weiteren politischen Diskussion die Befürchtung auf, der bei den öffentlichen Nichtwohngebäuden ab 2019 geltende Standard antizipiere den Standard, der für die übrigen Neubauten in einem weiteren Schritt bis 2021 eingeführt werden soll. Wegen der Diskussion im Kontext der Baukostensenkungskommission wurde hierin angesichts bevorstehender Wahlen politischer Zündstoff gesehen. Eine Gruppe von Abgeordneten der Koalition erreichte im Frühjahr 2017 eine Vertagung des Gesetzgebungsverfahrens auf die 19. Legislaturperiode. (Schettler-Köhler, 2021)</p> <p>Translation: In the subsequent political negotiations, the concern emerged that this proposed new standard for public non-residential buildings for 2019 indicates the standard that would be introduced for all other buildings by 2021. Following discussions of the commission for the reduction of construction costs, this was considered an explosive political issue for the upcoming electoral campaigns. In spring 2017, a group of Parliamentarians of the Coalition reached a postponement of the policy process to the 19th legislative period. (Schettler-Köhler, 2021)</p>
Policy agenda	Policy enables to control policy agenda and eases the business of governing other policy	Der Koalitionsvertrag zwischen CDU/CSU und SPD für die 18. Legislaturperiode vom 16. Dezember 2013 enthält zwei Fundstellen mit Bezug zum GEG: [...] Mit einer Baukostensenkungskommission überprüfen wir preistreibende und überdimensionierte Standards und Kosten von Materialien und Verfahren, insbesondere der energetischen

	processes	<p>Sanierung: (Schettler-Köhler, 2021)</p> <p>Translation: The coalition agreement between Conservatives (CDU/CSU) and Social Democrats (SPD) for the 18th legislative period contains two passages regarding the GEG: [...] We create a commission for the reduction of construction costs that reviews cost-increasing and overambitious standards for materials and processes, particularly of energy retrofits (Schettler-Köhler, 2021)</p>
Government values	Impact of the policy on the broad values and direction of government	<p>[...] ein neues Gebäudeenergiegesetz sollte die Anforderungen zusammenführen und vereinfachen. Zugleich war vorgesehen, mit dem Gesetz die Effizienzvorgaben für den Neubau öffentlicher Gebäude wie Schulen oder Krankenhäuser zu verschärfen. Im vergangenen Frühjahr wurde das Vorhaben jedoch abgeblasen, da CDU und CSU strengere Auflagen nicht mittragen wollten. Alles auf Anfang heißt es damit für die nächste Bundesregierung, die jetzt einen neuen Anlauf nehmen muss, das Regelwerk für die Energieeffizienz von Gebäuden zu reformieren. (Diermann, 2018a)</p> <p>Translation: [...] A new building energy act should merge and simplify requirements. At the same time, it was planned to increase efficiency requirements for new public non-residential buildings like schools or hospitals. Previous spring this project was cancelled, because the Conservatives (CDU/CSU) did not want to be responsible for the new obligations. This means „back to the start“ for the next federal government, which needs a new attempt to reform energy efficiency of buildings. (Diermann, 2018a)</p>
Opposition political	Opposition to the political benefits that the government obtained through the policy	No quotations

APPENDIX 4: Assessment of policy success

Table 7: Program success

PROGRAM SUCCESS	RESILIENT SUCCESS	CONFLICTED SUCCESS	PRECARIOUS SUCCESS	PROGRAM FAILURE
Implementation in line with objectives.	Implementation objectives broadly achieved, despite minor refinements or deviation.	Mixed results, with some successes, but accompanied by unexpected and controversial problems.	Minor progress towards implementation as intended, but beset by chronic failures, proving highly controversial and very difficult to defend.	Implementation fails to be executed in line with objectives
Achievement of desired outcomes.	Outcomes broadly achieved, despite some shortfalls.	Some successes, but the partial achievement of intended outcomes is counterbalanced by unwanted results, generating substantial controversy.	Some small outcomes achieved as intended, but overwhelmed by controversial and high profile instances or failure to produce results.	Failure to achieve desired outcomes.
Creating benefit for a target group.	A few shortfalls and possibly some anomalous cases, but intended target group broadly benefits.	Partial benefits realized, but not as widespread or deep as intended.	Small benefits are accompanied and overshadowed by damage to the very group that was meant to benefit. Also likely to generate high profile stories of unfairness and suffering.	Damaging a particular target group.
Meets policy domain criteria.	Not quite the outcome desired, but close enough to lay strong claim to fulfilling the criteria.	Partial achievement of goals, but accompanied by failures to achieve, with possibility of high profile examples e.g.	A few minor successes, but plagued by unwanted media attention e.g. examples of wastage and possible	Clear inability to meet the criteria.

		ongoing wastage when the criteria is efficiency.	scandal when the criterion is efficiency.	
Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is virtually non-existent, and/or support is virtually universal.	Opposition to program aims, values, and means of achieving them is stronger than anticipated, but outweighed by support.	Opposition to program aims, values and means of achieving them is equally balanced with support for same.	Opposition to program aims, values and means of achieving them outweighs small levels of support.	Opposition to program aims, values and means of achieving them is virtually universal, and/or support is virtually non-existent.

Adopted from McConnell (2010a)

Table 8: Process success

PROCESS SUCCESS	RESILIENT SUCCESS	CONFLICTED SUCCESS	PRECARIOUS SUCCESS	PROCESS FAILURE
Preserving government policy goals and instruments.	Policy goals and instruments preserved, despite minor refinements.	Preferred goals and instruments proving controversial and difficult to preserve. Some revisions needed.	Government's goals and preferred policy instruments hang in the balance.	Termination of government policy goals and instruments.
Conferring legitimacy on the policy.	Some challenges to legitimacy but of little or no lasting significance.	Difficult and contested issues surrounding policy legitimacy, with some potential to taint the policy in the long term.	Serious and potentially fatal damage to policy legitimacy.	Irrecoverable damage to policy legitimacy.
Building a sustainable coalition.	Coalition intact, despite some signs of disagreement.	Coalition intact, although strong signs of disagreement and some potential for fragmentation.	Coalition on the brink of falling apart.	Inability to produce a sustainable coalition.
Opposition to process is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal.	Opposition to process is stronger than anticipated, but outweighed by support.	Opposition to process and support are equally balanced.	Opposition to process outweighs small levels of support.	Opposition to process is virtually universal and/or support is virtually non-existent.

adapted from McConnell (2010a)

Table 9: Political success

POLITICAL SUCCESS	RESILIENT SUCCESS	CONFLICTED SUCCESS	PRECARIOUS SUCCESS	POLITICAL FAILURE
Enhancing electoral prospects or reputation of governments and leaders.	Favorable to electoral prospects and reputation enhancement, with only minor setbacks.	Policy obtains strong support and opposition, working for and against electoral prospects and reputation in fairly equal measure.	Despite small signs of benefit, policy proves an overall electoral and reputational liability.	Damaging to the electoral prospects or reputation of governments and leaders, with no redeeming political benefit.
Controlling policy agenda and easing the business of governing.	Despite some difficulties in agenda management, capacity to govern is unperturbed.	Policy providing controversial and taking up more political time and resources in its defense than was expected.	Clear signs that the agenda and business of government is struggling to suppress a politically difficult issue.	Policy failings are so high and persistent on the agenda, that it is damaging government's capacity to govern.
Sustaining the broad values and direction of government.	Some refinements needed, but broad trajectory unimpeded.	Direction of government very broadly in line with goals, but clear signs that the policy has promoted some rethinking, especially behind the scenes.	Entire trajectory of government is being compromised.	Irrevocably damaging to the broad values and direction of government.
Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually non-existent and/or support is virtually universal.	Opposition to political benefits for government is stronger than anticipated, but outweighed by support.	Opposition to political benefits for government is equally balanced with support for same.	Opposition to political benefits for government outweighs small levels for support.	Opposition to political benefits for government is virtually universal and/or support is virtually non-existent.

adapted from McConnell (2010a)

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